
GRADUATES UNEMPLOYMENT AND DEVIANCE IN KANO METROPOLIS: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

Unemployment among graduates is a serious phenomenon in Nigeria. It constitutes a problem not only for the graduates themselves, but to the overall social, political and economic structures of the country. The present study aimed at examining the causes and consequences of unemployment among the graduates in Kano metropolis. It also examines the reasons why some of them engaged in illicit activities. The role of government in eradicating this problem was also investigated. To ensure a comprehensive analysis of data, the study used a mixed method of data. This involved questionnaires and in-depth interviews administered to the unemployed graduates. Therefore, two hypotheses and four research questions were formulated to guide the study. A total of 217 respondents was utilised for the study and stratified random sampling was used to select the respondents. In addition to that, 10 participants were engaged in an interview and purposive sampling was used to select the participants. The questionnaire has a reliability coefficient of 0.80. The t-test at 0.05 level of significance was used in testing the null hypotheses. While thematic analyses were used for the interview. The findings of the study show that there is a significant relationship between unemployment and deviance. Unemployment among the respondents had both detrimental and beneficial effects on the unemployed graduates. The results show that they suffered from poverty, health and psychological problems. Furthermore, some of them became vulnerable to crime and deviance. However, unemployment also provided them an opportunity to be creative, resourceful and religious in order to cope with the crisis. In addition to that, the study also shows that despite the harsh effects of joblessness, only few of them were involved in illicit activities. Furthermore, the results also reveal that the government has a critical role to play in promoting the employability of graduates.

Keywords: Unemployment, graduates, youths, deviance

1. Introduction

Graduates in Nigeria are mostly youths who have successfully completed a course of study or training, and later been awarded a first university academic degree, National Certificates in Education and Higher National Diploma. Graduates are considered as future leaders and are usually acknowledged as the bedrock on which a society is anchored (Freedom, 2018). They are the locomotives of national development and they have the potential to stimulate economic and social growth of the nation (Alanana, 2019).

On the other hand, unemployment is a major problem affecting the generality of the populations in the country, particularly graduates of universities and tertiary institutions of learning. The majority of them spend years after graduation without employment (Udeh, 2021). These conditions lead to the involvement of some of them to illicit activities such as internet scamming, prostitutions, drug abuse and drug trafficking, illegal smuggling of petroleum products, rice, cars and other contrabands in to the country, illegal transactions of hard currency, racketeering and touting at the airports and bus stations etc., in order to earn a living.

Therefore, it is against this background that the paper examines the causes and consequences of unemployment and deviance among the graduates of Kano Metropolis and the role government plays in eradicating graduate unemployment in the state.

2. Objectives

The study has the following objectives:

- To examine the causes of unemployment among the graduates of Kano Metropolis.
- To investigate the consequences of unemployment on the graduates.
- To identify the reasons why some of the unemployed graduates resort to illicit activities.
- To examine the role of the government in eradicating graduate unemployment.

3. Hypotheses

The two null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study as follows:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between unemployment and deviance.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between graduates on the effect of unemployment and deviance.

4. Theoretical Explanations

Several studies related to unemployment have been acknowledged and different theories of unemployment have been clarified. These theories are important in providing the nature and causes of unemployment based on the perceptions and opinions of different schools of thought.

Therefore, the Marx theory of unemployment focuses on the causes of unemployment. Marx was of the view that the capitalist system caused unemployment in the sense that any expansion of output increased the demand for labour. In response to this demand, wages rose. But the manufacturers shifted the capital from wages to machines and discharged some of their workers who became what Marx called “a disposable industrial reserve army of unemployed” (Garraty, 2020). Marx argued that the system produced could not exist without this reserve army. He saw unemployment as an entirely normal and necessary aspect of capitalism, because he believed that unemployment is essential within the

unbalanced system of capitalism and the system is expected to experience mass unemployment crises periodically (Garraty, 2020).

While the Keynesian theory of unemployment states that technological improvement and specialization in skill-intensive goods enable the economy to satisfy a given (deficient) aggregate product demand with less labour input. Hence, employment will fall, and this leads to unemployment (Snower and De La Dehesa, 2019). Similarly, in his analysis of the causes of unemployment, John Maynard Keynes states that a variable person's "propensity to consume" tends to decline as income rises. Therefore, if all the increase in employment is devoted to making goods for consumption, production will outstrip demand and employers will be compelled to lay off workers. Lowering money wages could not reverse this trend; Keynes insisted that lower wages would mean lower prices, but fixed cost would remain unchanged; new investment will therefore be discouraged and unemployment will actually rise (Gordon, 2020).

Furthermore, based on the functionalist perspectives; unemployment is part of the disequilibrium and the result of the dysfunction of the social institutions. It is partly related to the failure of the family to inculcate the habit of workmanship and hard work of its members, resulting in a flawed value system towards work. It is also linked to a defective educational curriculum which fails to provide adequate employable skills. As part of the disequilibrium of the system, economic problem denies employment opportunities for the teeming population and the state policy does not emphasize empowerment of its citizens to become self-reliant. Therefore, these kinds of dysfunctions of the systems automatically lead to unemployment (Kendall, 2013).

5. Literature Review

Trends of Graduate unemployment

According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2018), the rate of graduate unemployment in Nigeria has continued to go upwards since from the year 2010. The reports stated that more than 50% of those who are unemployed in the country are graduates. Currently, another data published by the National Bureau of Statistics in 2020 have shown that a total of 52 million citizens in Nigeria is unemployed and this comprised mostly of new graduates.

Types of Unemployment

A review of related literature reveals different types of unemployment in Nigeria. For instance, according to Nkechi et al. (2022), frictional unemployment is triggered by roughness from the industries; this comprises problem of labour mobility, unaware of employment opportunities and failure of machinery. There may be existence of employments; however the workers may not be able to apply, either because they do not have the required skills or because they are uninformed about the existence of such employment. Furthermore, shortage of raw materials, shortage of electricity supply or mechanical defects of the working plants can lead to unemployment. However, cyclical unemployment is the result of the processes of the business cycle output. When the collective demand of the community falls below the productive capacity of the country, there may be inadequacy in buying full employment level of output. On the other hand, seasonal unemployment is also due to seasonal differences in the activities of certain industries triggered by climatic variations in style or by the characteristic nature of such industries. The ice factories, for instance, close down in winter, making workers unemployed because during the winter season the demand for ice is very low.

Causes of unemployment

Many scholars have examined the causes of graduate unemployment in several ways. For example, Ajaegbu (2022) claims that unemployment is caused by the decline of traditional skills and the deterioration of small scale industries. These problems lead to greater pressure on land and rural-urban migration, creating additional urban unemployment. However, Momoria (2018) states that, low level of investment and neglect of the industrial sector could not help the process of creating job opportunities.

Meanwhile, Madan (2020) discovers that unemployment is caused by personal and economic/technological factors. The personal factors, in his view, are simply the age factors which cause unemployment and limit the range of job opportunities. He explains that people at younger and older ages are both not eligible for many jobs. He also mentions that due to vocational unfitness many graduates do not have proper understanding of their aptitudes, abilities and interests as well as the jobs or careers they want to pursue. If readiness to perform some jobs is not followed by the necessary skills, one cannot discover a job of one's choice. Employers therefore, are always looking onward to get the person who possesses the interest, experience, physical fitness and ability to work.

In addition, there are also problems of illness or physical disabilities which cause unemployment. Graduates sometimes remain partially employed or totally unemployed throughout their lives due to the inborn or acquired disabilities or as a result of illness or accidents. Madan (2020) further states that the economic and technological factors of unemployment also relate to population growth. According to him, when the population is growing at an alarming rate, people who are eligible to work will not get the jobs due to intense competition.

Another contributing factor to graduate unemployment is the youth's unpreparedness to accept locally degrading jobs. Some youths, according to Mark (2019), are not prepared to undertake jobs which are considered socially 'degrading' or 'indecent' and sometimes below their qualifications. For instance, clerical office work, taxi driving, working as waiters, salesmen or sales girls, etc. Since they are not appropriately taught the essence of respect for work, they may likely face the danger of unemployment.

Consequences of unemployment

Unemployment is a serious problem that creates a number of consequences for the teaming graduate. For instance, Smith (2018) argues that unemployment is associated with an increase in crime as graduates find it difficult to meet their basic needs through work. Similarly, Sinclair (2020) reveals that there is a strong upward trend in both unemployment rate and certain reported crimes committed by youths such as burglary, theft, murder and rape.

Meanwhile, McClelland and McDonald (2021) found that unemployment has social and personal costs on the graduates. These include poverty, serious financial hardship, crime, alienation, homelessness, social isolation, shame and stigma, family tension and family breakdown, corrosion of confidence and self-esteem. Other consequences of unemployment are loss of self-identity, health problems and the problems of psychological well-being (Glyptis, 2021).

Similarly, Shaw et al. (2021) point out that due to unemployment, families suffer starvation by restoring to unbelievable economies in food. They claim that the physical health of the family members becomes impaired as a result of lack of proper nutrition and appropriate medical care. According to Jackson and Warr (2019), unemployment is a social

course and it may even pollute the economic and political fields. It causes the honest and energetic people to become dishonest, the distinguished and responsible people become irresponsible and unbecoming, the ingenious people become lazy and sluggish etc. The desire to do something in life becomes dehydrated.

In his study on unemployed graduates in Nigeria, Oshiomole (2014) states that when graduates have no job, they are deprived of the capacity to earn steady income and cannot live a socially productive existence. He further remarks that because of the absence of decent jobs, many of them are compelled to live indecent lives, sometimes as hardened and violent criminals or just as thugs available to be hired as assassins or be drafted into ethnic and communal clashes.

6. Methodology

The paper utilized mixed method of data collection as a research design. Therefore, the data was sourced through questionnaires which were administered to the unemployed graduates in six local government areas of Kano Metropolis, these are Fagge, Nassarawa, Dala, Kano Municipal, Tarauni and Ungogo local government areas. Similarly, data collected in the research was supplemented by a face to face interview with the unemployed graduates. The researchers employed the service of the research assistants to help with collecting data through the questionnaires.

The questionnaires and interview protocol are the instruments used for data collection. The questionnaire was developed by the researchers and tagged Graduate Unemployment Questionnaire (GUQ). It was divided into two sections; the first section contains the demographic information of the respondents, while the second section contains questions that bother with the research topic. Equally, the interview protocol comprises of the demographic information as well as the questions designed for the participants on graduate unemployment and deviance. Additionally, the interview conducted was semi-structured and was conducted with ten participants. The researchers employ purposive sampling as a technique for selecting respondents for the interview in order to provide the desired information by knowing the minds, opinions, attitudes and feelings of the respondents. The ideal population of the study consists of five hundred (500) unemployed graduates. The sample size for this research work are drawn from the ideal population and the research tolerates 5% margin error, thus 217 samples were used for the study based on the sample size determination of Krejcie and Morgan (1970). The stratified random sampling technique was used for the administration of the questionnaires and all the questionnaires were returned by the respondents. The instrument was validated by the experts in the area of measurement and evaluation to ensure content validity. Meanwhile, the reliability of the instrument was based on the Cronbach Alpha, which produced reliability co-efficient of 0.80. The result showed that the instrument was good enough to be used. The data collected from the respondent questionnaires were analysed using t-test analysis. While for the interview, the data collected were analysed using thematic analysis.

7. Results

The results of the study are based on the data collected from the two instruments used in this research (i.e. Questionnaires and interview protocol). However, the two null hypotheses were tested using the t-test analysis below:

Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁): There is no significant relationship between unemployment and deviance.

Table 1: Showing the t-test analysis between unemployment and deviance.

Variables	N	X	SD	DF	t.cal.	t.crit.	Decision
Unemployment	142	3.98	0.79	215	8.110	0.145	Significant
Deviance.	75	2.80	1.35				

Source: Field Work 2023

The result in table one above shows that the calculated t-test value of 8.110 is greater than the critical t-test value of 0.145 at 0.05 level of confidence. This implies that the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between unemployment and deviance, is rejected.

Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂): There is no significant difference between graduates on the effect of unemployment and deviance.

Table 2: Showing the t-test analysis between graduates on the effect of unemployment and deviance.

Variables	N	X	SD	DF	t.cal.	t.crit.	Decision
Unemployment	109	1.92	0.97	76	0.117	0.218	Not Significant
Deviance.	108	1.90	0.96				

Source: Field Work 2023

The data in table two above indicated that the calculated t-test value of 0.117 is less than the critical t-test value of 0.218 at 0.05 level of confidence. This implies that the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between graduates on the effect of unemployment and deviance, is retained.

In addition to that, the results of the interview gathered were presented and analyzed. The views of the respondents were examined based on the following subheadings:

The Causes of Graduate Unemployment:

The respondents gave their opinions on the causes of graduate unemployment. The themes that emerged from the respondent's explanation of the causes of graduate unemployment includes: Age discrimination, oversupply of graduates, government inefficiency, god-fatherism, and lack of demand for skilled labour.

On age discrimination, one of the respondents mentions that, it is a form of prejudice and stereotype against older people above 25 years old and younger individuals who have limited work experiences. He further stated that:

Since I am above 25 years of age, I failed to get employed in institutions such as banks, multinational organisations, oil companies and automobile industries because of the preference given to the younger applicants (22 to 25 years old).

On the issue of oversupply of graduates, this phenomenon occurred when the number of graduates seeking for employment exceeds the available job opportunities. One of the respondents has this to share:

If you consider the number of graduates coming out of the universities and other tertiary institutions in Kano and throughout the country in general, you will see that there is a surplus of labour in the market. The graduates will find it difficult to acquire jobs.

According to respondents government inefficiency here refers to the inability of the government to discharge its responsibility in tackling graduate unemployment. Although most of the government institutions are not functioning well to justify for more workers, the existing workers are always redundant in their places of work due to the government's negligence and lack of commitment. One of the respondents expressed his concerns as follows:

The government does not want to employ more workers because most of the staff in the ministries and agencies are not fully occupied. They are sitting redundant in the offices without any schedule of work or any assignment to execute. They only reported to their offices and at the end of the month, when the salary is paid.

Similarly, respondents believe that God-fatherism is a system of depending on a guarantor or someone who has a connection in order to get employment. He may be a politician, a wealthy individual or an influential figure in the State. As far as employment is concerned, some respondents considered it as a serious issue in Nigeria. In this system, it is not what you know that matters in seeking jobs, but it is whom you know. One of the respondents confirmed that:

The success of the graduates in search of a job depends upon their godfathers who can put them forward and struggle on their behalf. Anybody who doesn't have a godfather will find himself unemployed for many years.

The Consequences of Graduate Unemployment:

The themes that emerged from the respondent's explanation of the consequences of graduate unemployment include both positive and negative consequences. The positive ones are family cohesion, resourcefulness, creativity and spiritual life enhancement. While the negative ones are poverty, inferiority complex, depression and hypertension.

The study revealed that unemployment has generated positive consequence for the respondents. Unemployment has become an important instrument for family cohesion and family solidarity. The family members provided financial, emotional and moral support for the unemployed member. One of the respondents described his experience:

I do not have a problem with my family. They know that I am not working. At least they understand my problem. They all unite together to assist me with money and words of encouragement.

The respondents developed a strong sense of self-reliance in order to sustain themselves. This is manifested in their abilities to be resourceful and creative and engage in different types of income generating activities that benefitted them financially. The resourcefulness of the respondents can be gleaned from their efforts to engage in either self-employment, temporary employment or multiple jobs. One of the respondents narrated his experience as follows:

I have been self-employed since I graduated in 2015. I never believe in staying at home doing nothing. My job is to repair computers. The issue is that no matter how qualified you are if you are not working, people will never acknowledge your skill.

The study also found that some respondents earned income by engaging creatively in home crafts such as dying, weaving plaiting of hair and beads making. One of the respondents narrated her experience as follows:

I produce raw materials for dyeing at home. Out of which I make new clothes and sell them to office workers. I also advertise my products to ministries and organizations. This assists me a lot in solving my financial problems.

The study discovered that unemployment enhance the spiritual life of the respondents by bringing them closer to Allah through prayer, fasting and reading from the Holy Qur'an. These strengthened the religiosity of the respondents by reinforcing their faith and fear of God the Almighty. One of the respondents gave his own experience as follows:

I have become closer to Allah due to my desperate condition. I always pray five times a day, fast every Monday and Thursday. And also read one chapter every day from the Holy Quran all in order to purify myself and seek for Allah's forgiveness for the sin I committed. I always ask Him to solve my unemployment problem.

Another respondent added that fasting prevented him from doing something illegal or inappropriate. And it helps him to cope with frustration and anxiety caused by joblessness and made himself busy at home, to divert his attention from his unemployment condition.

However, the negative consequences of graduate unemployment are poverty, inferiority complex, depression and hypertension. The study found out that respondents experienced poverty as a result of unemployment. According to them, poverty deprived them of the proper opportunities and adequate means of subsistence in order to have healthy and satisfying life. These include inadequate income, limited household possession, hunger and malnutrition. One of the respondents described her experience:

I feel devastated by being jobless because I cannot support my family. I am the eldest in the family, but I cannot not help my parent financially. I am not comfortable because I graduated three years ago and yet I did not get anything meaningful in my life. So, unemployment is really affecting me.

The study discovers that some respondents suffered from inferiority complex due to unemployment. With their poor socioeconomic conditions, the unemployed respondents developed a strong feeling of inadequacy when they compared themselves to others with a stable job. One of respondents confirms that:

I am not comfortable to interact with my colleagues who were already employed. I felt that they were superior to me and I felt inadequate every time they assisted me financially.

The respondents mentioned that they experienced depression after spending years without a stable job. They mentioned that sometimes they suffered mental disturbances, anxiety, lack of interest in activities that were pleasurable before, loss of appetite and problems with concentration and memory. This is narrated by one of the respondents:

It is sometimes frustrating for me when I wake up in the morning and I have nowhere to go and nothing to do. This definitely forced me to think a lot about what to do. It is very depressing.

The study also exposed that some respondents suffered from hypertension and attributed their condition to emotional tension and stress associated with their unemployment. One of the respondents who suffered from this condition reported his ordeal:

Unemployment affected me psychologically and my overall health. One day, I had to see a doctor because of high fever, dizziness, weaknesses and nausea. After reading my blood pressure, the doctor informed me that I had hypertension.

Reasons for Graduates Involvement in Illicit Activities

The study revealed that some of the respondents could not endure the hardships and subsequent poverty brought about by unemployment. One of the respondents is involved in drug addiction to reduce tension generated by lack of jobs, the other engaged in illegal smuggling of rice into the country through border post. While, other two respondents engaged in internet scamming and prostitution respectively in order to generate income for themselves and their families. The reasons for their involvement in illicit acts include deprivation, frustration, feeling of rejection, lack of endurance and emotional trauma.

The dominant theme mentioned by the respondents as one of the causes for their involvement in illicit activities is deprivation. One of the respondents claimed that due to unemployment, he lacked basic things to live a comfortable life, such as adequate food, clothing, shelter and safety. In his words:

I am suffering from deprivation due to my long period of unemployment. I don't have money or material possessions to make my life comfortable. I cannot even have regular meals daily. This situation is just too much for me to bear. To reduce the tension, I smoke marijuana.

According to the respondents, another cause for their illicit acts is frustration. This involves the feeling of being upset or annoyed by their inability to fulfil a desire or a particular goal due to lack of money. Both the respondents agreed that frustration is a common emotional reaction to the difficulty that is associated with dissatisfaction with their present condition. It is the result of a continued struggle to survive in a difficult environment. Therefore, the greater the obstruction, the more the frustration is likely to be. One of the respondents explained that he was very frustrated as life was difficult without a job. Since he could not find a decent job, he resorted to internet scam and hacking to earn money. Similarly, another respondent mentioned that her involvement in prostitution was due to frustration. She further revealed that:

Unemployment triggers me to engage in prostitution because I am frustrated. And it is the same thing for some youths who go for armed robbery, cultism, bad gangs and other notorious activities. They did those acts out of their frustration due to their unemployment problem.

One of the respondents, involved in illegal smuggling of rice and other contraband due to his feeling of being rejected by the society, while another respondent admitted his involvement in illicit acts as follows:

I got involved in illegal transactions in hard currency to earn a living because I felt I was rejected by the society. I felt that the whole world was against me due to my unemployment, Sometimes, I would just sit down like a mad person thinking all day long what to do.

Respondents further explained that they experienced being ridiculed by their employed friends due to their joblessness. Sometimes, their associates simply ignore them or gave them a "silent treatment." This situation, they said, was just unbearable.

The study reveals that the inability of the respondents to withstand the hardship or unpleasant situation associated with their unemployment influenced them to engage in illicit behaviour. Both the respondents admitted that it was very difficult to endure the deprivation brought about by unemployment. As graduates, they aspired to get lucrative jobs after graduation and acquire material benefits similar to their friends who are working. Therefore, when the money to buy the material benefits was not available, they resorted to illicit activities to earn money. One of the respondents said that she could not endure the agony of unemployment. She also wanted to have a better lifestyle like her friends who were already employed. As a result, she decided to involve in human trafficking even though it is against the norm of the society.

The study reveals that emotional trauma is a consequence of unemployment. It is a psychological problem attributed to unemployed respondents after spending years of unpleasant unemployment experience. Emotional trauma makes respondents upset and anxious. One of the respondents expressed his opinion on the reason for his illicit behaviour:

I experience emotional trauma as a result of my unemployment. My mind started telling me to go and participate in one of the illicit acts that can bring me money. I'm confused; this kind of condition is intolerable.

Similarly, another respondent believed that his habit of racketeering in Aminu Kano International Airport is a result of his traumatic condition brought about by his nasty unemployment experience. He considered this experience as “a very shocking and disturbing situation.”

The Roles of Government in Eradicating Graduate Unemployment

Based on the perception of the respondents, the role of the government in eradicating unemployment among graduates includes creation of employment opportunities, empowerment and provision of loans to the unemployed graduates.

The study identified that the creation of employment opportunities is one of the major roles of the government in addressing the problem of graduate unemployment. This involves government efforts in providing employment to the youths. It requires generating more jobs and more economic activities to reduce crime and idleness among graduates.

According to some respondents it is the duty of the government to facilitate the empowerment of graduates. It is one of the important steps in tackling the problems of unemployment, particularly among the educated ones. Graduate empowerment is about capacity building and autonomy, which are very important approaches towards their development. The respondents believed that the government plays an important role in empowering the unemployed graduates to acquire various types of skills to augment their consciousness and partake in activities that will bring about community change. One of the respondents has this to say:

Youths stand a better chance of getting employed when they are knowledgeable and skilled. The majority of employers preferred graduates with the necessary knowledge and skills that can be trained and developed easily to take up the challenges.

The respondents believed that the government should provide the unemployed graduates with credit facilities so that they could become entrepreneurs. From his viewpoint, one of the respondents believed that the government's financial assistance would help unemployed graduates set up their own business. He informed that:

There is the need for the government to help its youths by giving them loans with no interest as a starting capital. This will reduce the rate of unemployment and poverty. The youths can become self-reliant rather than depend on the government.

8. Discussions

One of the findings of this study is that there was a significant relationship between unemployment and deviance. The result supports the assertion of Parker & Horwitz (2016) who opined that unemployment creates a stressful state that renders individuals susceptible to illicit activities in order to overcome their economic problems

Another finding of this study revealed that there was no significant difference between graduates on the effect of unemployment and deviance. This coincides with the findings of Blanchflower (2018) who argue that any society that alienates the largest segment and the most productive sector of its population (i.e. Youth), is neither sustainable nor tolerable. They would create serious misfortune, and the society would suffer the consequences. Similarly, this relates to the findings of Farrington et al. (2019) who contend that graduates are more likely to involve in immoral behaviours when living in an area of multiple deprivations. Thus, there is a strong connection between graduate unemployment and crime.

The findings of the study indicate that unemployment in Nigeria is caused by many interrelated factors. The study shows that age discrimination contributed a lot to the joblessness of the respondents. This corresponds with the findings of Wood et al. (2018) who found out that age discrimination was widely accepted as a major cause of unemployment. According to them, many eligible graduates were discriminated because they were above the age limit set aside by the employers. The employers of labour preferred younger and energetic graduates who could serve for a long period of time in the company. This situation encouraged graduates to change their birth certificates in order to meet the criteria of the employers.

The study finds out that oversupply of graduates prevented the majority of respondents from securing employment due to competition among job seekers. This is similar to the findings of Venatus and Agnes (2020) who confirm that Nigeria has continued to witness a surplus of graduates in the labour market which has resulted in rapid growth of the labour force that exceeds the amount of employment opportunities available.

The government inefficiency, has not produced an enabling environment for most of the manufacturing sectors to function well, so as to employ more workers. This is similar to the findings of Nkechi et al. (2022) who insist that the non-existence of a vivacious manufacturing sector causes graduate unemployment in Nigeria.

The findings of the study also reveal that scarcity of vacancy in most private and public sectors is due to nepotism in the country. Respondents believed that children of the elites among them secure employment without difficulty since they have somebody to stand for them. But children from poor families, no matter how qualified they are could not succeed since nobody can stand for them. This is similar to the findings of Anyanwu (2020) who observe that what is destroying job opportunities in Nigeria is nepotism. It is due to our insistence on using the wrong people for the wrong jobs. We now see our country through the prism of our tribes and states. Job seekers are not employed on merit, but rather on favouritism which causes damage to the graduates as future leaders in the country.

On the other hand, the findings of the study clearly reveal that the consequences of unemployment. One of the consequences of unemployment is poverty. In this situation, most of the respondents experienced difficulties in fulfilling their basic necessities of life, such as food, clothing and shelter. This is similar to the findings of Mukwuzi and Agbo (2022) that many individuals and families in Nigeria could not meet their basic needs in life due to unemployment. This is due to the fact that many graduates who struggled to complete their higher education ended up unemployed in spite of their qualification.

In terms of health consequences, the findings of the study show that many respondents experienced unstable health conditions due to unemployment ranging from hypertension, depression and devastation. This is similar to the findings of Nickell (2019) who points out that unemployment damages physical, mental and moral health of unemployed people. They may not get sufficient food and medical assistance to maintain good physical health. Likewise, it also relates to the findings of Glyptis (2021) who identifies that the social consequences of unemployment among youths involve the stigma and loss of self-esteem, loss of self-identity, health problem and the problem of psychological well-being.

9. Conclusion and Recommendations

The importance of graduates as agents of social change in the development agenda cannot be over-emphasized. The rate and degree of unemployment at present time depicts that the future of the graduates is bleak in Kano State and Nigeria in general. It is evident from the above analysis that graduate unemployment is a chronic problem which seriously undermines peace and national security of the country. At present, Nigeria suffers serious security challenges posed by the graduates due to their involvement in illicit activities. This calls for the government to re-organise, educate and mobilise youths for development. The government should be committed to introduce policies and programmes that best address their issues and concerns. It is only through these measures that their trust and confidence could be restored, thereby contributing their potential to nation building.

However, the paper made certain recommendations for the benefit of policy makers, stakeholders and change agents in order to address the problem of graduate unemployment in Kano State in particular and Nigeria in general.

- 1.** The Kano State government must play its constitutional role in combating unemployment among graduates. It is absolutely essential for the government to have a link with micro-finance banks and other financial institutions, in order to establish functional and efficient microcredit scheme for the youths. The banks may be authorized to allocate certain percentage of their loan facilities for the unemployed graduates to start a business. Therefore, this will significantly reduce graduate unemployment and also assist in minimizing rural-urban migration among graduates.
- 2.** The increasing rate of unemployed graduates in Nigeria necessitates the creation of more employment opportunities. Therefore, there is the need for Kano State government to have a comprehensive list of all unemployed graduates in the state, with different areas of specializations and skills. The data obtained could be used by the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) and employment generation agencies to place appropriately each and every capable applicant in the jobs.

- 3.** The Kano State government should establish the enabling environment for the private sector to flourish. This could be through the provision of socioeconomic infrastructure such as electricity, telephone, roads and housing, particularly in the rural areas.
- 4.** Another way to create employment for the graduates is through agriculture. The graduates should be encouraged to participate in agriculture with modern farming tools and better yielding crops. The government should establish agricultural centres in all the 44 local government areas of the state that could employ thousands of graduates. These agricultural centres could be serviced and supported by small scale industries. For example, setting up of rice processing and canned tomato industries in a centre where there is large scale irrigation of rice and vegetables like Kura irrigation centre in Kano state. This will stimulate mass production of rice and tomatoes and also influence non-farm related jobs.
- 5.** Unemployed graduates themselves have a greater role to play in eradicating unemployment in Kano State because the government alone cannot successfully deal with their problem. In order to solve unemployment, their support and cooperation is required toward this direction. Unemployed graduates should be trained to be tolerant and hardworking in their quest for employment by engaging in activities that will allow them to earn a living and never indulge themselves in illicit activities. Therefore, employment cannot be possible if youths are lazy and unable to put any meaningful effort in making themselves self-employed.
- 6.** The attention of the graduates should be drawn in order to exercise patience and be self-content. They should learn to endure and be self-satisfied with the little jobs they are doing in order to make themselves self-reliant. The idea of self-reliance is an important step in building their confidence by providing them with moral and financial support. In addition, let them realize that government jobs are not forthcoming. They have to engage themselves in small scale business so that they can generate income for themselves and their families.

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